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CIRCULAR VALORIZATION OF INVASIVE MACROALGA *SARGASSUM MUTICUM*: A MARINE BIOMASS RESOURCE FOR SUSTAINABLE AQUAFEED PRODUCTION

Dan Cristian VODNAR¹, Nikoletta TRICHA², Chrysanthos STERGIOPOULOS^{2*},
Marina STRAMARKOU³, Sofia PAPADAKI², Bianca-Eugenia STEFANESCU¹,
Lavinia Florina CĂLINOIU¹ and Magdalini KROKIDA²

¹ Inspire Science SRL, Razoare 207A, Cluj, Romania

² Prinsus IKE Technoblastos, Iroon Polytechniou 9, 157 80 Athens, Greece

³ Food Chemistry and Technology Department, Teagasc Food Research Centre, Scribbletown,
Dublin 15, Ireland

*Corresponding author, e-mail: chrisxp3@hotmail.com

Introduction: *Sargassum* spp. brown algae blooms, invasive in Europe and North America, intensified by eutrophication and ocean warming, pose ecological challenges but offer valuable biopolymers such as alginate, fucoidan, and laminarin. These polysaccharides have gelling and antioxidant properties suitable for bioactive encapsulation. Olive leaf extract (OLE), rich in phenolics, is bioactive but unstable, requiring protection for practical aquafeed application.

Aims: This study aimed to design and assess microparticle systems based on *Sargassum* polysaccharides for the stabilization and release of OLE in aquafeeds.

Materials and Methods: Polysaccharides were sequentially extracted from *Sargassum muticum* and purified by ethanol precipitation and dialysis. OLE was extracted using 70% ethanol (1:20 w/v) and analyzed for total phenolics (Folin–Ciocalteu), antioxidant activity (DPPH), and phenolic composition (HPLC). Microparticles were formed by CaCl₂-induced ionic gelation using i) alginate, ii) alginate–fucoidan, and iii) alginate–fucoidan–laminarin matrices. SEM, FTIR, size analysis, and encapsulation efficiency via TPC were used for characterization. In vitro digestion simulated pH 3–7.5 of *Dicentrarchus labrax*.

Results: Yields were 21.6% w/w dry mass alginate, 7.8% w/w dry mass fucoidan, and 4.2% w/w dry mass laminarin. OLE yielded 15.3% w/w dry mass extract with 73.5 mg GAE/g phenolics and 851.6 μmol TE/g antioxidant activity. Encapsulation efficiency rose from 62.4% (alginate) to 85.1% (ternary). The ternary matrix retained 91.4% antioxidant activity and showed controlled release: 28.5% phenolics at one hour and 68.1% at four hours, versus >85% burst in alginate-only systems.

Conclusion: *Sargassum muticum* polysaccharides can effectively encapsulate OLE for aquafeeds. The ternary matrix showed superior efficiency, protection, and sustained release. This approach promotes circular valorization of marine and agro-industrial biomass in sustainable fish nutrition.

Keywords: aquafeed, encapsulation, polysaccharides, *sargassum muticum*, sustainable aquaculture.

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